

An Empirical Study on the Effectiveness of Software Bug Reports: A Registered Report

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Abstract

Debugging (i.e., identifying and repairing bugs in software) often relies on artifacts – such as test case reports – generated to help developers in understanding program behaviour. Although such reports are widely used in practice, it remains unclear how different *report types* affect debugging performance and perception. To address this gap, we design a human-subject study comparing three report types, namely test case reports, counterexample traces, and textual descriptions. Participants complete four debugging tasks on small Java programs, each task supported by one of these report types. The study aims to consider both objective outcomes and subjective outcomes to provide empirical evidence on how report types influence human debugging and to inform the design of future debugging support artifacts.

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1 Introduction

Debugging – the process of localizing and repairing the cause of a software failure (bug) – has always been a time-consuming and expensive task in software development. Despite the many existing fault localization techniques and the tendency to automate the debugging process, the results are usually limited to ranked suggestions based on the suspiciousness of code elements rather than definitive answers. As a result, manual code review remains necessary in most cases.

In practice, bugs are often investigated with the support of generated reports, e.g., test results, execution traces, verification outputs, and natural-language explanations [7, 22, 29, 30, 31, 36]. These help developers understand program behaviour and speed up the debugging process. However, these reports differ substantially in the type of information they provide and in how they support debugging and bug repair tasks.

Understanding the effect of different forms of reports is therefore particularly relevant in the context of debugging. Despite the use of such bug reports in practice, it remains unclear how different report representations affect human debugging performance and decision-making. Existing evaluations often assess whether a report can be generated, but they do not necessarily show how well the report supports a human in identifying and repairing a bug [1, 7, 32]. Moreover, a report that is effective for identifying a functional bug may not be equally effective for locating its root cause or selecting an appropriate repair.

To address this gap, we design a *controlled human-subject study* that compares the effects of three report types on debugging and bug repair tasks. To this end, we plan to conduct the study via a web platform in which participants work on four small, buggy Java programs,

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identify bug locations, and possible fixes. Participants are provided with different types of reports that may support them in completing these tasks.

The study considers both objective outcomes, such as correctness, and subjective outcomes, such as perceived helpfulness and report preference. In doing so, we aim to provide empirical evidence on how report representation influences human debugging and how developers evaluate different forms of support for identifying and repairing functional bugs, and to guide the design of more effective debugging support.

2 Background

In this section, we introduce the sort of bugs we are interested in and the types of debugging reports considered in this study.

A *functional bug* is a defect in a program that causes it to fail to perform its required function or to produce behaviour that deviates from the expected functional specification [20]. In this study, we solely focus on defects that cause a program to violate its expected behaviour, although the program remains executable.

For this study, we focus on three different report types:

Test case reports give example-based evidence through passing and failing program behaviours. They provide specific inputs together with expected outputs or behaviors that are used to check whether a program works correctly. By executing a program with these inputs and comparing the observed results to the expected ones, test cases help detect faults and validate intended behavior [4, 12].

Counterexample traces provide execution-based evidence by exposing an erroneous execution path together with relevant values. Here, a flow-graph-like diagram depicts the execution trace of a counterexample, where the nodes represent the program statements executed along the counterexample path and the edges capture the values of local variables during execution [5, 9, 16, 23].

Textual descriptions provide explanation-based support in natural language, reflecting the growing use of large language models for programming explanation tasks [22, 24]. They are typically generated automatically from program code, execution information, or analysis results, and summarize relevant aspects of program behaviour in a human-readable form.

These report types represent three distinct forms of support for identifying and understanding functional bugs and correspond to three common sources of debugging information, namely software testing, formal verification, and natural language explanation. All three report types can provide information relevant to the early stages of debugging, in which a developer determines whether a program exhibits incorrect behaviour. Also, limiting the study to three report types helps the feasibility of the within-subject design and avoids splitting participant's attention across closely related sub-variants (e.g., several different forms of test cases). Other report categories would be valuable comparisons as a direction for follow-up work.

3 Research Questions and Hypotheses

This study examines how report type relates to debugging outcomes and participant evaluations in the context of functional bugs. This study is guided by the following research questions:

RQ1. Do developers' debugging performance differ across report types?

H1a. Localization correctness differs across report types.

H1b. Repair correctness differs across report types.

We hypothesize that report types which make the faulty execution path more explicit may support localization differently from those that describe the behaviour more abstractly. Also, since report types differ in how directly they communicate the intended program behaviour, we hypothesize that these differences may affect repair accuracy.

RQ2. Do participants' perceptions and evaluations differ across report types?

H2a. Perceived helpfulness during localization differs across report types.

H2b. Perceived helpfulness during repair differs across report types.

We hypothesize that report types which are more familiar to participants, more directly support the localization task or contain repair-relevant information may be perceived as more helpful during localization and repair.

H3a. Participants' post-task report-type preferences are associated with the report types under which they showed higher localization and repair correctness.

H3b. Participants' per-task perceived helpfulness ratings are associated with localization and repair correctness on those tasks.

If participants can accurately assess which reports supported their debugging process, we hypothesize that their preference rankings and perceived helpfulness ratings will align with their observed performance.

Hypotheses H1a and H1b are the confirmatory hypotheses for this study. The other hypotheses are treated as exploratory. For each of the three hypotheses, the corresponding *null hypothesis* **H0** assumes no effect of report type on the respective outcome.

4 Study Design

In this section, we discuss the material used to conduct our study, the participants and their eligibility, the procedure followed in our study and its tasks. Finally, we also outline the variables from the study that help us prove or disprove our hypotheses. The study protocol has been approved by the institutional ethics committee.

4.1 Materials

The study materials consist of the benchmark programs, the bug reports, and the web-based study platform through which participants complete the tasks.

Dataset. The programs for the tasks are taken from the QuixBugs benchmark [25]. The benchmark consists of 40 programs, each containing a single-line bug and a description of the program's expected behaviour. For this study, we excluded programs with recursive structures or nested loops in order to improve readability and enable quicker comprehension by participants. After preprocessing, the final set comprised four programs. The selected programs range from 17 to 35 lines of code. Our design intentionally constrains program complexity, structure and bug type to support experimental control under the feasibility constraints of an unmoderated online study and to mitigate fatigue. We revisit this limitation in Section 8.

Bug Reports. The three report types selected for this study are *test case report*, *counter-example trace*, and *textual description*.

Test Case Report Test case reports are constructed using the test cases provided with the benchmark. Each report includes one passing test case and one failing test case fixed per program.

Counterexample Trace Counterexample traces are typically produced by software verifiers. For each program, we give a flow-graph like diagram depicting a collapsed version of the execution trace of a counterexample, where the nodes represent the program statements executed along the counterexample path and the edges capture the values of local variables during execution.

Textual Description To evaluate the effectiveness of LLM-generated explanations, we include a report containing a textual description of the functional bug in the program produced by an LLM. For this study, such reports are generated using OpenAI's GPT-5.1 model with a fixed zero-shot prompt [27].

Study Platform. All materials are delivered through a web-based application developed for the study using Spring and TypeScript. The platform presents the programs, the associated task information, and the report artifact when applicable. It also records participant responses, timing information, report ratings, and post-task feedback. All participants interact with the same platform interface throughout the study. The platform ensures the randomized assignment of task configurations, report types, and task order.

The selected Quixbugs programs and generated reports are available as an artifact at zenodo¹.

4.2 Participants

The study targets participants with a basic understanding of software programming. Recruitment will proceed through open calls, including posts on online forums. Potential participants include students, volunteers, external collaborators, and industry acquaintances. Participant background information is collected through the pre-task questionnaire. Participation is voluntary and the participants will not be compensated in any manner. Only participants aged 18 years or older are eligible to participate in accordance with privacy-related requirements for the collection and handling of study data. The study does not collect direct identifiers such as names or email addresses and the identifying session information is not linked to a particular participant. This design choice supports the anonymous handling of study data and ensures participants' privacy. As a result, repeated participation cannot be ruled out at the individual level. We rely on the self-reported screening question to mitigate repeated participation.

4.3 Procedure

Figure 1 summarizes the study flow. After accepting the data-processing acknowledgement, participants complete a pre-task questionnaire. The acknowledgement also contains a screening question asking participants whether they have previously completed the study and discloses that re-participation is discouraged. The questionnaire collects demographic and background information followed by their self-reported confidence in solving programming problems. This is followed by a tutorial task that familiarizes them with the main tasks.

Each participant then completes four main tasks. Among the four tasks, three tasks involve buggy programs paired with one of the three report types. The remaining task

¹ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20137326>

■ **Figure 1** Overview of the study procedure.

Top: overall study flow. Bottom: within-task procedure for the four main tasks

consists of a buggy program without any report which provides a baseline for evaluating the value of report-supported debugging. The order of the tasks is randomized for each session. For each task, the description of the program along with its preconditions and the expected output is provided.

Each task is divided into three phases:

Examination Phase During the examination phase, participants inspect the provided program and determine whether it contains a bug. Participants may choose to run the provided program with their own custom inputs during the examination. At the end of the examination phase, participants answer the question: “*Does this code contain a bug?*” with ‘Yes’ or ‘No’. Participants may take as much time as needed to complete their examination. However, when a participant spends more than five minutes, the platform displays a pop-up asking whether additional help is required. The task proceeds to the localization phase if the participant explicitly clicks ‘Yes’ assuming that the participant did not find the bug. Else, the participant moves to the localization phase upon completing the examination phase.

Localization Phase In this phase, participants must identify and select the line in the program that contains the bug from a drop-down list. If one of the report types is assigned to the task, the corresponding report is shown during localization. Participants may take as much time as needed to complete this phase.

Repair Phase At this point, the platform provides feedback on the participant’s localization answer and the report remains available. The participants have to repair the buggy line of code with the correct patch to achieve the expected behaviour of the program. Participants select the correct repair from a list of four candidate solutions. Repair correctness is interpreted as *patch selection accuracy given the bug location*. Revealing the correct buggy line allows us to isolate reasoning about candidate fixes from errors in bug localization. The incorrect patches are generated by applying mutations to variables, operators, or operands at the buggy line.

For tasks with a report, the participants are asked to rate the helpfulness of the provided report on a 5-point likert scale at the end of the localization phase and repair separately.

■ **Table 1** Primary variables used in the study

Variable	Description
Independent variables	
Report type	Type of report assigned to a task: test case report, counterexample trace, or textual description.
Dependent/Measured variables	
Localization correctness	Whether the participant correctly identifies the buggy line (binary).
Repair correctness	Whether the participant selects the correct repair (binary).
Report helpfulness for localization	Whether the participant finds the assigned report helpful during localization (1-5 likert scale).
Report helpfulness for repair	Whether the participant finds the assigned report helpful during repair (1-5 likert scale).

The custom-inputs help simulate a realistic debugging experience, in which developers are typically able to run and inspect programs with inputs of their own. This functionality is conceptually distinct from the test case report. While the test case report provides a fixed, static summary consisting of pre-selected passing and failing test cases, the custom-input execution allows participants to interactively explore the program behaviour as they would while debugging in the real world.

After all four tasks are completed, participants fill in the post-task evaluation. They are then asked to rank the report types according to their preference. Finally, participants indicate whether they have used any AI tools while completing a task.

4.4 Variables and Measures

The variables used in the analyses are summarized in Table 1. The main independent variable is the report type assigned to a task, with three variants: *test case report*, *counterexample trace*, and *textual description*.

In addition to the primary variables, the study records participant background information through the pre-task questionnaire, including age group, region, educational background, programming experience, and self-reported programming confidence. The post-task evaluation further collects report preference rankings, ratings of task understandability, platform ease of use, and program difficulty, all on 5-point Likert scales. Finally, the study records whether participants use custom inputs during the task and whether any task is completed with AI-based assistance through self-declaration. These additional variables are used to characterize the participant sample and to support analyses.

As participants complete multiple tasks in sequence, task order is included as a control variable to capture overall order effects, including possible learning and fatigue. Aggregate participant-level measures derived from the task-level outcomes may be used in exploratory analyses if needed.

5 Pilot Study

We conducted a pilot with four PhD-level participants, with varying levels of experience in solving programming problems, to assess feasibility of the study and platform usability. After

completing the study on their own, the participants provided feedback in the presence of two of the authors. Their responses indicate that the overall study procedure is understandable and that the platform is easy to use. On average, each participant took approximately 40 minutes to complete the study. The participants indicated that the original five-task design imposed fatigue, so we reduced the study to four tasks. 2 of the 4 participants also emphasised the need for users to try their own inputs against the provided program during debugging. Based on this observation, a custom-input execution feature is made available for all programs in the main study. Finally, minor UI/UX refinements and better descriptions were added to improve the platform. Data from the pilot study is excluded from the main analyses.

6 Execution Plan

The study will be deployed as a web-based platform accessible to participants through an online link. Data collection will remain open for a fixed period of two months. Since the final sample size is constrained by practical considerations of a voluntary open-call study, we aim to recruit participants from sources such as student volunteers from bachelor and master degree programs, open calls on public forums like LinkedIn and Reddit and through industry acquaintances and collaborators.

For each session, the platform will generate a task configuration consisting of three buggy-program tasks paired with three different report types and one control task. Each session will remain active for a maximum of two hours. If a participant does not complete the study within this time limit, the session will be terminated automatically. Responses, timing information and task-level interaction data will be recorded.

A session will be considered invalid if any of the following conditions apply: (i) the session times out and is terminated before completion, (ii) the participant reports AI- or LLM-based assistance for any task in the session, or (iii) the recorded completion time for each task is less than 60 seconds, which is treated as an indication that the participant may have selected responses without meaningfully engaging with the task. Invalid sessions will be excluded from the analyses.

7 Analysis Plan

The analyses are designed to address the research questions and the corresponding hypotheses. All analyses will be conducted on the cleaned dataset described above. We will report descriptive summaries separately on participants' background variables, correctness rates, custom-input usage, completion times, helpfulness responses, and preferences, for each report type.

Power Analysis. Simulating a power analysis for the selected mixed effects logistic model with an intraclass correlations of 0.20 [17], $\alpha = 0.025$ (Holm corrected false positive rate [19]), power $1-\beta = 0.80$, and a target minimum detectable effect of approximately 30 percentage points between the report types [28], the analysis yields a required **sample size of N=70 participants**. We acknowledge that effects substantially smaller than this threshold may not reach significance. Since the effect size is also constrained by the recruitment feasibility of our open-call study, non-significant results will be interpreted via observed effect sizes with 95% confidence intervals.

Data Preparation. Before the main analyses, the collected data will be filtered according to the predefined criteria in Section 6. Only valid completed sessions will be retained.

Aggregated variables will be derived only after the task-level data has been cleaned and validated.

For retained sessions, records will be organized at the task level together with assigned program and report type. Primary outcomes are examination correctness, localization correctness, and repair correctness. Report-helpfulness ratings for localization and repair, where applicable, will also be added at the task level. Participant-background variables from the pre-task questionnaire and subjective ratings from the post-task evaluation will be linked to the corresponding task-level records.

Confirmatory Analysis. The binary outcomes of the two confirmatory hypotheses (H1a and H1b) are influenced by three fixed effects - the program (4 selected programs), the report type (3 types), and the order of the tasks. The variability in programming proficiency of the participants is considered to be a random effect. To model an analysis for the hypothesis, we use a mixed-effects logistic regression model for binary outcomes, as it correctly models the nature of the response while accommodating both fixed and random effects[21]. If the mixed effect model cannot be estimated reliably due to less than expected participants, we resort to Cochran's Q test [13] (for robustness) which evaluates the same hypotheses without taking the fixed-effects (program, task order) into account.

Exploratory Analyses. For the exploratory analyses of hypotheses H2 and H3, we resort to the widely used [35] Friedman's test [15] and Spearman's rank correlation [34] respectively. For H2, Friedman's test is used as the outcome is ordinal(Likert scale) and supports smaller sample sizes. For H3, Spearman's coefficient is used in order to measure subjective preferences against objective performance. All exploratory analyses use uncorrected $\alpha = 0.05$.

In addition to the planned analyses, the study may further examine associations between participant-related factors and the measured outcomes, including demographic variables, platform usage, aggregated measures, localization and repair time, and other derived relationships. Such analyses will be treated as descriptive and reported accordingly.

8 Threats to Validity

The proposed study is subject to the following threats to validity and practical limitations. First, participant background differences, such as programming experience and confidence, may influence debugging performances independently of the assigned report type. To reduce this threat, the study adopts a within-subject design in which each participant encounters all three report types exactly once. In addition, task order and report assignment are randomized.

A further threat arises from repeated participation, since the study does not collect identifying information in order to support anonymous handling of study data. To mitigate repeated participation, we include a pre-task screening question asking participants whether they have previously completed the study. Also the study will consider unrealistic short task durations as invalid sessions. We rely on these design choices and on the limited motivation for repeated participation to minimise the practical impact of this threat.

Since the correct buggy line is revealed during the transition from the localization phase to the repair phase, the repair task measures constrained patch selection rather than fully independent bug fixing. The study simplifies debugging into examination, localization, and repair phases in order to improve control and comparability, although this may not fully reflect real-world debugging practices.

The study uses a small subset of the QuixBugs benchmark and excludes complex programs for cognitive effects of program complexity on debugging performance [33] and to maintain

a feasible session length and avoid any fatigue, as reported by the pilot study participants. As a result, our findings are limited to Java programs with simple control structures and single-line bugs. Generalisation to programs with nesting, recursive structures, larger size or more complex bugs should be made with caution and will require follow-up studies.

Finally, some measures, such as report helpfulness, report preference, and AI-use disclosure, rely on self-report and may therefore be affected by reporting bias.

9 Related Works

Developer-centric studies show that debugging requires substantial effort and benefits from effective support artifacts. Böhme et al. [11] study how practitioners localize and fix bugs, while Alaboudi et al. [3] and Hirsch et al. [18] report that developers spend considerable time inspecting code and need better localization support. This motivates human-subject evaluations of debugging support.

Prior work has investigated developers' testing behaviour in the IDE to find and locate bugs and how developers interpret unreliable test outcomes [6, 14, 2]. These studies highlight that testing artifacts are important sources of evidence that developers use when debugging.

In formal verification, analysis tools commonly generate counterexamples or violation witnesses to describe erroneous executions [5, 9]. Prior work has investigated how such artifacts can better support debugging, for example through executable counterexamples and explanation-oriented representations [16]. Kaleeswaran et al. [23] further emphasize the need for better explanations of verification artifacts, especially for non-experts. Recent work has extended this direction by improving witness usability: Beyer et al. [10] perform fault localization on verification witnesses to reduce witness complexity and improve understandability; Beyer et al. [8] generate executable tests from witnesses for execution-based validation.

Beyond automated bug fixing, LLMs have been studied as tools for explaining program faults [26], including generating natural-language summaries of source code [22]. Kang et al. [24] report that developers prefer to receive bug explanations from LLMs before attempting repairs.

In practice, developers encounter bug evidence in other forms as well. Stack traces, static-analysis warnings, issue-tracker descriptions provide bug information at various stages of the software development lifecycle. Overall, debugging artifacts from various debugging support tools and their effectiveness are often studied in isolation and the support provided by artifacts is rarely compared. This motivates our comparative study of how different report types support human debugging tasks with a stronger emphasis on developers' perception and evaluation of such reports, including perceived helpfulness and preference. We aim to better understand not only whether a report is effective, but also how it is experienced and valued by developers during debugging.

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